

The Role of Polymeric Phenol as Antioxidant in Hydrocarbon Oxidation

Durgasankar Chakrabarti and Uma Shankar Nandi

In recent years it has been observed that the behaviour of a monomeric substance is quite different from that of its polymer. Sakurada^{1,2} has shown in a series of papers that in the hydrolysis of esters, polymeric sulphonic acids have greater catalysing activity compared with that of hydrochloric acid under exactly similar experimental conditions in aqueous solutions. Overberger³ also reported that benzimidazole reacts quite differently from polyvinyl benzimidazole both in order and in character.

In the above context of the relative behaviour of monomer and the corresponding polymer the behaviour of polymeric phenol seems to be interesting as far as its role as antioxidant is concerned in oxidation systems and the present communication reports some results on this project.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of polymeric phenol : Polymeric phenol has been prepared by the reaction of anhydrous ferric chloride with monomeric phenol according to the procedure of Gerhard F. L. Ehlers⁴. The structure of the polymeric phenol is

the molecular weight of the compound being around, 10,000.

Tetralin was oxidised in solutions of dioxane at 60°. Oxidation was followed by oxygen uptake measurement in a modified apparatus as described by Hammond *et al.*⁵, the oxygen pressure of the whole system being automatically maintained constant electronically.

1. Ichiro Sakurada *et al.*, *Kubunshi Kagaku*, 1965, **22**, (247), 698, 701, 706, 711.
2. I. Sakurada *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1965, **22**, (248), 804, 808.
3. C. G. Overberger, T. St. Pierre and S. Yaroslavsky, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, (19), 4310; C. G. Overberger *et al.*, *Trans. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1965, **27** (7), 790.
4. Gerhard F. L. Ehlers, Preprints of Scientific Papers, International Symposium on Macromolecular Chemistry, Tokyo Kyoto, 1966, II-9.
5. George S. Hammond, Charles E. Boozer, Chesler E. Hamilton and Jyotirindranath Sen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3233, 3238.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When equivalent amounts of phenol or polymeric phenol (concentrations expressed in terms of phenol) was used, the antioxidant character showed significant difference even though the phenolic content remaining same in both the cases. A typical set of experiments is represented in Fig. 1. It may be visualized that both the rate of oxidation during the

a and b represent polymeric phenol and phenol of equivalent concentration ie, 3.34×10^{-3} in all cases.
 ABN = 0.1M in 1 and 2
 = 0.05M in 3
 Tetralin = 1.21M in 2
 2.42M in 1 and 2

Fig. 2

ABN = 1.67×10^{-2} in all cases
 Tetralin = 3.64M in all cases
 Polymeric phenol = 0.66×10^{-3} M in (1)
 1.67×10^{-3} M in (2)
 3.34×10^{-3} M in (3)

induction period as well as the period of induction differed considerably and inhibition by polymeric phenol is rather sharp, similar to that of a strong antioxidant. Experiments conducted under varying concentrations of the initiator (i.e., 2,2'-azobisisobutyronitrile), tetralin and polymeric phenol clearly demonstrated that the polymeric phenol behaves much more efficiently than phenol. A typical set of experimental results are presented in the Table.

TABLE

Comparison of the rates of oxidation of Tetralin initiated by ABN in solution of dioxane in presence of phenol and polymeric phenol at 60°.

Oxygen pressure = 750 mm.

[Tetralin] mole/L	[ABN] $\times 10^2$ mole/L	[Phenol] $\times 10^3$ mole/L	[Polymeric* phenol] $\times 10^3$ mole/L	Initial rate of oxidation $R_0 \times 10^6$ mole/L/sec.
2.42	10.00	—	—	6.19
2.42	10.00	3.34	—	3.98
2.42	10.00	—	3.34	1.736
1.21	10.00	3.34	—	2.17
1.21	10.00	—	3.34	0.437
2.42	5.00	3.34	—	3.11
2.42	5.00	—	3.34	0.94
3.64	1.67	1.67	—	2.86
3.64	1.67	—	1.67	0.726
3.64	0.42	1.67	—	1.37
3.64	0.42	—	1.67	0.171

ABN = 2,2' azobisisobutyronitrile

* Concentration expressed in terms of Phenol.

Fig. 2 represents results on the oxidation of tetralin studied with different concentrations of polymeric phenol. The behaviour of polymeric phenol is comparable with standard antioxidants, the inhibited rate of oxidation and the length of the induction period being relatively proportional to the concentration of polymeric phenol.

Thus it might be inferred that polymeric phenol at least in tetralin oxidation behaves like a normal antioxidant except that it is more efficient and long lived than its corresponding monomer i.e., phenol.

From similar work on the hydrolysis of esters, Sakurada and co-workers have concluded that the higher efficiency might be due to the high localised concentration of the acid.

That it might be also true in the case of polymeric phenol can be explained on the basis of higher efficiency as antioxidant. The high local concentration of polymeric phenol might suppress the rate of oxidation but it is certain that this is not the complete picture as evidenced from the longer inhibition period in the case of the polymeric antioxidant. This point is receiving close attention in this laboratory.

Department of Macromolecules,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Calcutta-32.

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